

Republic of Yemen
Sana'a University
graduate Studies
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Characteristics of Intelligent Buildings and their Applicability to Yemeni Architecture

Case Study (Building of **The Central Organization for Control
(and Accounting - Sana'a**

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Abstract:

The beginning of the eighties is considered a qualitative leap in the architecture field, which was the beginning of the appearance of intelligent buildings. These buildings expressed the scientific and technological progress that humanity has reached in architecture. The building can know, decide, and respond to the environment self-reliant until the concept of the intelligence in the buildings arrives to achieve sustainability and take into account the surrounding environment. With these new concepts in the architecture, this thesis aims to study the characteristics of these intelligent buildings and what it has reached from a scientific and technical progressional standpoint, as well as study the possibility of applying the characteristics of the intelligent buildings on the buildings of the contemporary Yemeni architecture to benefit from the advantages of these intelligent buildings to upgrade the performance of our Yemeni buildings.

This research contained five chapters. The first chapter presents a comprehensive theoretical idea about intelligent buildings in terms of the concept of intelligence in it and a history of the evolution of this intelligence, as well as identifies the properties of these intelligent buildings as their importance and features, finally evaluate the intelligence of the building through standards which developed by specialized organizations to give a certificate for the degree of intelligence of the building.

The second chapter presents the basic requirements to build an intelligent building capable of self-management and responsive to the surrounding conditions with efficiency and taking into account the local environment by studying the intelligent construction system (intelligent systems, intelligent skins, intelligent materials) and what is the digital infrastructure needed to activate the work of this intelligent system.

In the third chapter, the previous theoretical study is applied through an analytical study of existing intelligent buildings (Regional, global) by studying the intelligent system in these buildings and their differences from one building to another, where the results of the third chapter are used in the fourth chapter, in which the practical study of this research is conducted by studying the contemporary Yemeni architecture to apply the characteristics of intelligent buildings on it through studying the reality of contemporary architecture, informatics and technology in Yemen, that were represented in studying of the construction system in these Yemeni buildings (systems, facades, materials) to draw the most essential problems which our Contemporary Yemeni

architecture experiences, then a detailed study for the Building of Central Organization for Control and Accounting (COCA) as a building represents one of the Contemporary Yemeni buildings to apply the characteristics of intelligent buildings on it by knowing the adequacy of the infrastructure and the extent of possibility of the building to achieve an intelligent construction system to be put forward proposals of the development and the promotion for the building.

Finally, in the fifth chapter, a summary of the study is prepared from the re-results of the theoretical and practical aspects of the study, and the recommendations that included various parties as well as identifying the beneficiaries from the study, then the suggestions for future studies in the same field.